

Technical report

User Journey Extension for Archimate (UJEA)

Lars van den Bos¹, Marcela Ruiz² [0000-0002-0592-1779], Jan Martijn van der Werf¹,
Rob Douwes³

¹ Utrecht University, The Netherlands
{l.vandenbos@students.uu.nl; J.M.E.M.vanderWerf@uu.nl}@uu.nl

² Zurich University of Applied Sciences, Switzerland
marcela.ruiz@zhaw.ch

³Rabobank, Utrecht, The Netherlands
rob.douwes@rabobank.nl

This report serves to provide additional information to the paper: An Extension to Archimate: integrating User journeys with Enterprise Architectures. The report provides additional insights about the design and development of User Journey Extension for Archimate (UJEA).

User Journey Extension for Archimate

User Journey Extension for Archimate is an extension of Archimate that integrates user journey maps into the enterprise architecture domain. We start this report with a high-level overview of the design (Chapter 1), followed by an evaluation of the harvested requirements (Chapter 2) from the literature study, case study and expert interview. The evaluation leads to a final list of requirements. Next, we structure user journeys by formulating a list of user journey concepts (based on literature study and practical findings), followed by a user journey meta model that shows the relationships among concepts (Chapter 3). We proceed by investigating Archimate (Chapter 4), in which we analyse its structure, element types and concepts. At last, we create User Journey Extension for Archimate (Chapter 5). The artefact consists of i) a mapping of user journey concepts to Archimate concepts, ii) an extended Archimate framework, iii) a meta model that with user journey and Archimate concepts, iv) a graphical notation and v) a cross-layer meta model.

1. Design approach

We start our treatment design by shaping a treatment design procedure, providing a high-level overview of the creation of the artefact User Journey Extension for Archimate (UJEA).

1.1. High-level approach - UJEA

For creating User Journey Extension for Archimate, we follow the high-level design procedure, shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: High-level procedure for creating UJEA

The procedure shows the required inputs for the artefact, the creation of the artefact and the artefact possibilities. Additionally, the corresponding chapter sections are shown in each step. The design procedure is agile, meaning we do not have to necessarily finish a step to jump to the next, and that we can always go back to a previous step. Iterative development is believed to be a fundamental rule when it comes to developing a set of user journey concepts or meta model [1].

We start our design by finalizing the initial requirement list from section 3.4 (step 1). The initial requirement list was constructed by combining all possible solutions and ideas found in the literature study and practical investigation. For our artefact, we only want to keep necessary, valuable requirements that fit the artefact and purpose in mind. Thus, each initial requirement will be evaluated and either kept or dropped. For the evaluation, we look at the supporting literature and practical sources. Additionally, initial requirements are evaluated and complemented by members of The Open group (Appendix A). As result, we have a final list of requirements for building our artefact, as well as a final list of user journey concepts (as REQ 1-31 entail user journey related- or user journey specific concepts).

Next, we provide structure to user journeys (step 2). As user journey concepts were part of initial the requirements, we can derive our user journey concepts from the final requirement list. Next, we establish and visualise the relationships among the user journey concepts. The list of user journey concepts and the relationships among user journey concepts are both essentials for creating the meta model in which we extend Archimate with user journey concepts. Hence, the user journey concepts and meta model are inputs for UJEA.

Having our user journey concepts and meta model, we also need to explore the Archimate structure and concepts in order to connect Archimate with user journey concepts. Hence, we examine the Archimate structure and concepts (step 3). We explore Archimates element types and concepts and derive their descriptions from the Archimate specification document [2]. The descriptions will be used when we start mapping Archimate to user journey concepts; as we will compare concept descriptions to find a match for each concept. Additionally, we will derive the visual hierarchy of Archimate element types that we will use as input for our UJEA meta model.

When we are finished with collecting the required inputs for the artefact, we can start creating User Journey Extension for Archimate (step 4). The artefact consists of 5 main components:

- *Mapping of concepts*: Linking Archimate element types and concepts to user journey concepts.
- *UJEA meta model*: A meta model that visualises the mapping of concepts and the relations among the user journey concepts.
- *New Archimate Framework*: The new user journey domain integrated into the Archimate framework.
- *UJEA graphical notation*: Visualising the shapes, icons and colours of the user journey elements in Archimate.
- *Cross layer meta model*: Shows the allowed relationships with Archimate elements from other layers.

The approach for creating UJEA will be explained in further detail in section 4.5.

At last, we describe the applications of UJEA (step 5). There are different analyses possible the UJEA that will be explained. We finish the design by explaining how UJEA can be a solution to align UX designers with architects.

2. Requirements

As first step of our design procedure, we evaluate the initial requirement list to select a subset of requirements with sufficient support that we will actually implement. This results into a final requirement list that we will use to create our artefact, as well as our list of user journey concepts since user journey specific elements are also included in the initial requirements list.

2.1. Evaluation of requirements

For determining the final requirements and user journey concepts, we evaluate the initial requirement list that was harvested from the literature study, case study and expert interview. For additional evaluation of our initial requirements, a discussion session was arranged with some members of The Open group. Although the discussion session was mainly supposed to evaluate the initial requirements, the session also lead to six new requirements, that can be found in Appendix A. The new requirements concern the structure of user journey maps, the mapping of user journey concepts to Archimate and decisions for designing the graphical notation. Although these requirements were derived from The Open Group, we will still evaluate them whether they are fit for our artefact. The results/notes from the discussion can be found in Appendix A.

The evaluation of initial requirements is shown in Table 1, containing the initial requirements (ID and description), design decisions along with a rationale for each design decision. For the initial requirements (Req 1-44) are evaluated by i) literature support, ii) practical support, and (sometimes) by iii) the opinions of The Open Group. The newly added requirements from The Open Group (Req 45-50) are evaluated by literature support and findings in practice.

Table 1: Evaluation of requirements list

ID	Description	Requirements evaluation	
		Design decision	Rationale
Req1.	The artefact should support User journeys	Accept	Even though customer journeys seem more popular according to our problem investigation, user journey maps are the former version of customer journey maps and thus provides a start (that can later be extended with customer journeys).
Req2.	The artefact should support Customer journeys	Reject	Despite the significant evidence that customer journey maps are popular frequently practiced among UX design and Architects, we scoped our thesis on the former version of customer journeys (user journeys) and keep the idea of extending to customer journeys for future research.
Req3.	The artefact should support Buyer journeys	Reject	The literature study, case study and the JourneySoftware interview showed that buyer journeys are used at marketing, not at UX design and enterprise architecture.
Req4.	The artefact should support Planned journeys	Accept	The case study showed that UX designers and architects mainly create planned journeys.
Req5.	The artefact should support Actual journeys	Reject	The case study and the JourneySoftware interview showed that actual journey maps are not common at UX design and enterprise architecture.
Req6.	The artefact should support Journey concepts	Reject	Insufficient reason found in the literature study and practical investigation. Although the terminology study at ContextMSP showed that this concept is applied, we did come across this concept in the other interviews.
Req7.	The artefact should support Scenario(s)	Reject	Insufficient support found in the practical investigation.
Req8.	The artefact should support Persona(s)	Accept	The literature study and practical investigation showed that personas are a common element for user- and customer journey maps. Additionally, persona was seen as a necessary element by The Open Group.
Req9.	The artefact should support Touchpoints	Reject	Despite significant recognition in both literature study and practical investigation, the case study and JourneySoftware interview introduced the overlap between Touchpoint and Channel. After discussing this issue with The Open Group, the decision was made to go for channel (Req10) to at least show what communication medium is used.
Req10.	The artefact should support Channels	Accept	Significant recognition of concept in both literature study and practical investigation. During the session with The Open Group, the choice was made to choose for channel and drop touchpoint (Req9), to at least show the used communication medium. Additionally, channel was seen as a necessary element by The Open Group.
Req11.	The artefact should support Stages	Accept	Sufficient support from the literature study and practical study. Stage was present in almost every discussed example in section 2.4, present in the example of JourneySoftware, and present in the examples of UX designers. Additionally, stage was seen as a necessary element by The Open Group.
Req12.	The artefact <i>must</i> support Experience	Accept	This must-have requirement was derived from one of the UX interviews, stating that experience differentiates journey maps from customer flows. Our definition of user

			journeys directly supports this statement. Additionally, experience was seen as a necessary element by The Open Group.
Req13.	The artefact should support Moment of truth	Accept	Common element found in the practical investigation. Both JourneySoftware, and ContextMSP showed that moment of truth is a common element for journey maps.
Req14.	The artefact should support Deviations	Reject	This is an element of actual journeys (Req5), which we decided not to implement. Additionally, practical investigation shows little support for this concept.
Req15.	The artefact should support Breakpoint(s)	Reject	This is an element of actual journeys (Req5), which we decided not to implement. Additionally, the literature study and practical investigation showed little support for this concept.
Req16.	The artefact should support an Initiator	Reject	Initiator was only recognised at ContextMSP but not present in the example customer journeys. Additionally, literature support was limited and as the user journey is seen from the user's perspective, the journey should always start with the user (that is already represented by Persona).
Req17.	The artefact should support a Trigger	Reject	The concept seemed familiar to JourneySoftware and ContextMSP. Though, literature support is little, the element was not present in the case study/journeysoftware examples, and "the idea to trigger a journey" is relatable to Goal (Req18) we choose to implement.
Req18.	The artefact should support a Goal	Accept	Recognised and applied at both JourneySoftware and ContextMSP and was seen as a necessary element by The Open Group.
Req19.	The artefact should support Timeline of the journey	Accept	Used at JourneySoftware and Recognised at UX designers of ContextMSP. Though we did not come across this concept among the UX and architect journey examples, the timeline was present in the example discussed at the The Open Group, as attribute for each stage. Hence, we accept this concept.
Req20.	The artefact should support Time of Touchpoints	Reject	Insufficient literature and practical support. Concept was only recognised at JourneySoftware, which is part of actual journeys (and thus out of scope).
Req21.	The artefact should support Traces	Reject	Trace was not found in the practical investigation, with only one literature source supporting it.
Req22.	The artefact should support Notes	Reject	Note was not found in the practical investigation, with only one literature source supporting it.
Req23.	The artefact should support Opportunities	Accept	Opportunity was present in the UX journey map examples, present in one of the journey map examples in the literature study (2.4) and recognised as concept by JourneySoftware.
Req24.	The artefact should support Internal ownerships	Reject	Internal ownership was added as it was found in an example discussed in the literature study (2.4). Though this concept was not found in other literature and neither in the practical investigation.
Req25.	The artefact should support Lens(es)	Reject	Lens was not found in the practical investigation, supported by only one literature source.
Req26.	The artefact should support a flow of interactions	Accept	Necessary to show the order of interactions/actions of the customer. A flow was present in every examined journey example.
Req27.	The artefact should support Information points	Reject	Information point was added to the requirement list as it was found in the journey example of LEGO to indicate a moment where data is required. Though, as we aim to connect architecture to journey elements, we can already link data elements to journey elements.
Req28.	The artefact should support Activities (individual steps the user takes)	Accept	Although literature support is scarce, the practical investigation showed that both JourneySoftware and ContextMSP are using activities to show the actions of the user, that simultaneously entail interaction between service provider and user, i.e. Touchpoint. As we dropped touchpoint due to its similarity with Channel, we use activity to represent both the user actions, as well as the interaction through a channel. Additionally, activity was seen as a necessary element by The Open Group.
Req29.	The artefact must support the Abstraction level of a user journey	Accept	Abstraction level was added as missing element by the architect at ContextMSP. Additionally, abstraction level was seen as a necessary element by The Open Group.
Req30.	The artefact should support thoughts	Accept	Thoughts found in two examples in the literature study, and in both UX customer journey map examples.
Req31.	The artefact should support pain points	Reject	Discussed in the session with The Open Group, pain points should not be included into planned journeys as it requires detailed analysis. Additionally, negative experience will already indicate similar information to the reader.
Req32.	Experience should be visualised by the colours red, yellow and green.	Accept	The use of these colours to indicate experience was observed from multiple examples in practice and literature.
Req33.	Experience is determined by the position on the Y-axis	Reject	In the discussed journey examples, the Y axis was used for channels and experience. Positioning elements on the Y-axis to indicate experience was seen in multiple literature examples, as well as in UX design journey examples at ContextMSP. Though, Archimate has no semantics to the height of elements, except the order of type of elements described in the Archimate layer framework. As we have Req. 32 and 34 as alternative options for experience, this requirement is dropped.
Req34.	Experience should be represented by emoticons	Accept	The use of emoticons was observed from many examples, both in the literature study and the UX design journey map examples.
Req35.	Channels should be visualised with swimlanes on the Y-Axis	Accept	In the discussed journey examples, the Y axis was used for channels or experience. We saw sufficient examples (literature study, JourneySoftware, ContextMSP) where channels were depicted as swimlanes.

Req36.	Stages should be visualised on the X-axis, on top of the journey	Accept	Stages were visualised this way in every example that included stage as concept.
Req37.	Touchpoints should be visualised on the X-axis	Reject	Touchpoint (Req9) was rejected. Instead of touchpoints, activity will serve as the interaction/user action.
Req38.	User journeys should be modelled in or connected to the Business layer	Accept	Supported by the architect of ContextMSP, it is only logical to position the journey above the business layer as the business services are the services used by customers.
Req39.	The user journeys made with Archimate should be static like Archimate	Accept	We dropped the idea of supporting actual user journeys (Req5), and have decided to scope on planned user journeys (Req4)
Req40.	The artefact should support omnichannel journeys	Reject	As user journeys are single channel, this requirement does not fit the scope of this thesis but remains a suitable requirement for extending to customer journeys (as future work).
Req41.	The artefact should support traceability links between user journey elements and architecture components.	Accept	The traceability links between journey and architecture helps architects to assist UX designers with technical analysis/advice. The idea of tracing journeys back to architecture was the reason why the architects at ContextMSP created a customer journey framework for architects.
Req42.	The artefact must be understandable by both UX designers and Architects	Accept	To improve the communication between UX designers and architects, both parties have to be able understand the models. As Archimate is a language from the architects, it would be best to meet familiarity aspects of UX designers as well.
Req43.	The artefact must be compatible with Archimate standards and concepts	Accept	As the artefact is supposed to extend Archimate, this requirement is kept.
Req44.	The user journey should match the level of abstraction of the architecture	Reject	Together with The Open Group, we decided to create predefined abstraction levels that the creators who use UJEA must comply to. It is up to the creator to choose one of the abstraction levels, instead of basing the abstraction level on the underlying architecture.
Req45.	To map user journey concepts to Archimate, first map the new concepts to element types, then map them to Archimate concepts.	Accept	Classifying concepts this way helps us to narrow down the possible matching concepts, and map the concepts in a more structured way.
Req46.	If touchpoint is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a Business service (behavioural, and external)	Reject	For the scope of this thesis, Touchpoint (Req9) has been rejected. However, this requirement could be used for further research when extending Archimate further to support customer journeys.
Req47.	If channel is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a Business interface (structural)	Accept	A business interface is a point of access where a business service is made available to the environment [2]. The description matches perfectly with the purpose of a channel.
Req48.	If activity is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a business service (behavioural, and external)	Accept	An alternative candidate was a business process: "a sequence of behaviors to achieve a specific outcome" [2]. However, a business process is internal, while a business service can be external (and the user's actions are external from the company's perspective). Additionally, according to the Archimate meta model, business services can trigger business services as well, creating a series of external behaviors.
Req49.	If persona is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a role (structural)	Accept	A business role is the responsibility of performing specific behavior, to which an actor can be assigned, or the part an actor plays in a specific action or [2]. The description matches the idea of a persona, that represents a user type with certain properties, characteristics and behavior.
Req50.	If experience is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a metric	Accept	A metric is the extent, quantity, amount or degree of something, as determined by measurement or calculation [2]. This matches the idea of experience that can have different emotions as values.
Req51.	An abstraction level should be included with predefined levels	Accept	As abstraction levels are difficult to specify, predefined levels like "high-level" vs "low-level" would be helpful for creating and reading the user journey map.

2.2. Final requirement list

To establish the final requirement list for our artefact, we exclude all rejected requirements from Table 1. As result, we have a final requirement list of 29 requirements in total, shown in Table 2. The requirement ID's are kept the same, so that the corresponding rationale for each requirement can easily be traced back.

Table 2: Final requirements list

Final requirement list	
ID	Description
<i>Req1.</i>	The artefact should support User journeys
<i>Req4.</i>	The artefact should support Planned journeys
<i>Req8.</i>	The artefact should support Persona(s)
<i>Req10.</i>	The artefact should support Channels
<i>Req11.</i>	The artefact should support Stages
<i>Req12.</i>	The artefact <i>must</i> support Experience
<i>Req13.</i>	The artefact should support Moment of truth
<i>Req18.</i>	The artefact should support a Goal
<i>Req19.</i>	The artefact should support Timeline of the journey
<i>Req23.</i>	The artefact should support Opportunities
<i>Req26.</i>	The artefact should support a flow of interactions
<i>Req28.</i>	The artefact should support Activities (individual steps the user takes)
<i>Req29.</i>	The artefact should support the Abstraction level of a user journey
<i>Req30.</i>	The artefact should support thoughts
<i>Req32.</i>	Experience should be visualised by the colours red, yellow and green.
<i>Req34.</i>	Experience should be represented by emoticons
<i>Req35.</i>	Channels should be visualised with swimlanes on the Y-Axis
<i>Req36.</i>	Stages should be visualised on the X-axis, on top of the journey
<i>Req38.</i>	User journeys should be modelled in or connected to the Business layer
<i>Req39.</i>	The user journeys made with Archimate should be static like Archimate
<i>Req41.</i>	The artefact should support traceability links between user journey elements and architecture components.
<i>Req42.</i>	The artefact must be understandable by both UX designers and Architects
<i>Req43.</i>	The artefact must be compatible with Archimate standards and concepts
<i>Req45.</i>	To map UJ concepts to Archimate, first map the new concepts to element types, then map them to Archimate concepts.
<i>Req47.</i>	If channel is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a Business interface (structural)
<i>Req48.</i>	If activity is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a business service (behavioural, and external)
<i>Req49.</i>	If persona is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a role (structural)
<i>Req50.</i>	If experience is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a metric
<i>Req51.</i>	An abstraction level should be included with predefined levels

As we finished our requirement list, we can focus on the inputs for our artefact. For the artefact, we need to have an overview of the user journey concepts, descriptions and relations and, as well as the Archimate concepts, descriptions and relations. In the next section, we focus on structuring user journeys.

3. Structuring user journeys

Having our final set requirements, we still need filter and define the user journey concepts and their relations as we need this input for our artefact.

3.1. Final user journey concepts

The remaining requirements from Table 2 that entail user journey concepts are Req8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 18, 19, 23, 28, 29, and 30. These requirements almost contains our final set of concepts. As last step, we split user journeys (Req1) into *user journey* and *user journey map* as this provides structure to how user journeys are managed: there is a difference between an explicit and inexplicit user journey. User journeys are merely a concept whereas user journey maps are documented visible user journeys. As explained in Chapter 2, the user journey is the total of experiences across time (inexplicit), whereas a user journey map is a documented user journey (explicit). As result, we have our list of user journey concepts shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Final list of user journey concepts

User journey concept	Definition / meaning	Corresponding Req.
<i>User journey</i>	The total user experience (emotions, perceptions and feelings) across a period of time, as the user interacts with a product or service to achieve a goal using a system. [10,11,12]	<i>Req1.</i>
<i>User journey map</i>	Visualization of experiences people have when interacting with a product or service by using a system [12].	<i>Req1.</i>
<i>Persona</i>	Representation of a typical user that contains motivations, goals, pain points and other characteristics [4].	<i>Req8.</i>
<i>Channel</i>	A medium for users and service providers to interact with one another [9].	<i>Req10.</i>
<i>Stage</i>	Container of multiple activities to indicate a phase of the journey.	<i>Req11.</i>
<i>Experience</i>	Emotions and scale of emotions [3].	<i>Req12.</i>
<i>Moment of truth</i>	Decision points that can make or break the success of the journey. It can be a simple decision, or a hard decision that is experienced as a barrier [4].	<i>Req13.</i>
<i>Goal</i>	The thing what the user aims to achieve, such as obtaining a loan in a banking context, this is the final touchpoint of a service [4].	<i>Req18.</i>
<i>Timeline</i>	Duration of the journey from the starting touchpoint to the final touchpoint. The timeline can be depicted by actual time or ordering touchpoints by giving them numbers [3].	<i>Req19.</i>
<i>Opportunity</i>	A suggested improvement.	<i>Req23.</i>
<i>Activity</i>	A user action.	<i>Req28.</i>
<i>Abstraction level</i>	The level of detail of a user journey map, determined by the creator that wants to inform the reader how the user journey map should be read.	<i>Req29.</i>
<i>Thought</i>	Representation of a user's thinking. They explain or add extra information to the emotions of the user.	<i>Req30.</i>

We now have our final list of user journey concepts. With the artefact we aim to build, we need to know the relationships among the user journey elements, as not every element can just be linked to every element. For example, we want to relate emotions to activities, not to a channel. Thus, certain rules need to be created in which we specify the possible relationships between elements. A way to structure the (allowed) relationships among elements, is creating a meta model. Hence, we create a user journey meta model that we will later integrate into our artefact.

3.2. User journey meta model

The user journey meta model is shown in Figure 2. The meta model shows an overview of the user journey concepts, relations and cardinalities. The presented concepts are derived from the list of user journey concepts (Table 3): *user journey*, *user journey map*, *abstraction level*, *persona*, *goal*, *channel*, *stage*, *timeline*, *activity*, *opportunity*, *moment of truth*, *thought* and *experience*. The attributes of the concepts are documented separately due to readability reasons.

Figure 2: User journey meta model

Starting at the top, we see that user journey is presented in italics unlike the others. This is because user journey is an *abstract concept*; it cannot be instantiated and just serves to provide structure and context to the meta model. Where a user journey is the implicit journey of experiences of the user (the concept), a user journey map is a documented, explicit user journey, and thus can be instantiated.

A user journey map is always associated to *one* specific user journey, but a user journey can be associated (represented) by *multiple* user journey maps. This is because there can be multiple visualisations of the same user journey. A user journey map can have many different elements, of which some are optional while others are mandatory. As *mandatory* elements; a user journey map must always have one goal, one channel, an abstraction level and at least two activities (otherwise there is no flow). A user journey cannot have multiple channels as single-channel was one of the conditions of a user journey. However, this could be an easily adjustable element for future research to extend to customer journeys.

As for *optional* elements, a user journey map can have opportunities, stages and a timeline. These elements are kept optional as there is not always an opportunity to identify and we have examined and observed multiple examples without stages or timelines. Further, a user journey map *can* be associated to a persona. A persona is kept *optional* in case the architect wants to create a quick user journey just to show a customer flow with experience and does not want to make a full description of a persona. This decision was based on the journey example of architects at ContextMSP, that did not include a persona (probably to spare time). On the right of the model, we see that the optional timeline can either be presented on the whole user journey map (to show the total duration), or on each stage (which allows to map multiple timeframes). This decision was also based on the examined examples.

Moving to the bottom of the meta model, we see that a stage must have at least one activity, and a channel must have at least two activities. A stage without an activity would be redundant, and a channel with one activity would not be a flow. We also see a trigger relation from the activity to itself. This relation allows a flow of activities in the user journey map (that trigger one another). Further we see that an activity *must* have an experience and *can* have a moment of truth and a thought. The experience is made mandatory as a user journey without experience would become a customer flow. A thought and a moment of truth are kept optional as we only saw these elements in a few journey examples.

The attributes that belong to the user journey concepts are shown in Table 4. Most attributes are strings, even Time (attribute of Timeline) is chosen to be a string. By choosing strings, we give as much freedom to the users as possible when the user journey meta model is implemented (in our artefact for example). Leaving some freedom and space to potential users instead of putting restrictions on attributes could contribute to potential implementations by making it easier to use.

Table 4: User journey meta model attributes

User journey meta model attributes			
User journey concept	Attribute	Type	Description
<i>User journey</i>	Name	String	Name of the user journey.
	Description	String	Additional information to the user journey. The creator is free to decide what additional information to add.
<i>User journey map</i>	Name	String	Name of the user journey map. It can be the same name of the corresponding user journey but this is not necessarily the case; there can be multiple user journey maps made for the same user journey.
	Description	String	Additional information to the user journey. The creator is free to decide what additional information to add.
<i>Persona</i>	Name	String	Name that represents a type of customer.
	Properties	String	Characteristics that specify what type of customer the persona represents.
	Goals	String	General motives or goals in life, or related to products/services/systems of the service provider.
<i>Channel</i>	Name	String	Name of the used channel. This has to be a digital channel/system.
<i>Stage</i>	Name	String	Name of the stage.
<i>Experience</i>	Emotion	Enumeration	A set of named experience values: {Happy, Neutral, Unhappy}. For simplicity reasons, we now stick to only three values, but more could be introduced later if requested by experts.
<i>Moment of truth</i>	-	-	As a moment of truth is contained by an activity, which on its turn can be further explained by a corresponding thought. As both the activity and thought already provide sufficient information about an important decision made, it would become redundant or unnecessary complex to name or add text to a moment of truth.
<i>Goal</i>	Name	String	Small description of the desired outcome of the user journey.
<i>Timeline</i>	Time	String	The time a process or journey should take, expressed in what the creator seems fit (secs, mins, hours, days, months, years).
<i>Opportunity</i>	Name	String	Name of the opportunity.
	Description	String	Additional information to the opportunity; what corresponding software the opportunity belongs to, which people/business functions/teams should be appointed for further action etc.
<i>Activity</i>	Name	String	Name of the activity. This entails a description of the interaction between the user and a digital channel (app, website, etc).
<i>Abstraction level</i>	Level	String	Two predefined levels: <High level> and <Low level>. The levels serve as guidance from creator to reader; instructing from what level of detail the user journey map is made and thus how it should be read. There are however no strict rules to follow; the level serves as guidance to read the user journey map. The idea of using predefined levels was based on the notes of The Open Group session (appendix A).
<i>Thought</i>	Name	String	A description of the user's thought when an activity (interaction with a system of the service provider) is executed.

As we finished our attributes table, we have now brought structure to user journeys: we created a final list of user journey concepts, a meta model showing the relations and a table of attributes for each concept. Before we start to integrate user journeys into enterprise architecture, we need to select and explore an enterprise architecture language. This will be elaborated in the next section.

4. Archimate

As our SQ2 stated, we want to create a user journey integrated architecture language. The enterprise architecture language chosen for our artefact is Archimate. In this section, we explain why Archimate is chosen, we give an introduction of Archimate to provide some context, and examine its element types and concepts. The latter two contain vital information for mapping the user journey concepts onto Archimate concepts.

4.1. Why Archimate?

Archimate is a common modelling language among enterprise architects. Many organizations are using it as their company company standard for describing enterprise architecture, and its value has been proven in practice [5]. Furthermore, there is significant tool support for Archimate [6] and the language was chosen as the standard for the enterprise architecture method TOGAF. At last, Archimate allows customization of the language that is tailored towards specific domains and applications. To customize the language, one has to create new elements and map these onto existing Archimate elements [2].

4.2. Introduction to Archimate

Archimate is an Enterprise Architecture modeling language that provides a uniform representation for diagrams describing the architecture of an (mostly large sized) company [6]. Archimate includes a set of concepts, meta models, specifications for inter-related architectures, specific viewpoints for selected stakeholders, and specifications on how the language can be further customized. By specifying a structure and relations between different layers and specifying viewpoints, Archimate allows different architecture domains to be connected in one visualisation. Archimate is structured by the *Archimate Framework*. The framework is a structuring mechanism for architecture domains, layers, and aspects. It distinguishes between the model elements and their notation, to allow for varied, stakeholder-oriented depictions of architecture information (Archimate® 3.0.1 Specification, 2019). Originally, the core framework only contained three layers: the business layer, application layer and technology layer. In the past years the core framework has been extended multiple times, resulting into the *Full Archimate Framework*. The Full Archimate Framework is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The Full Archimate Framework [2]

The framework is structured into two dimensions: *Layers* and *Aspects*. A layer represents a specific domain that contains a structure of elements and relationships, whereas aspects represent type of elements. The specified layers in the framework are Strategy, Business, Application, Technology, Physical, Implementation & Migration and Motivation [7]:

- *Strategy layer*: Contains strategic elements such as capabilities, resources and courses of action.
- *Business layer*: Contains business services offered to customers, realized by organizational processes and actors.
- *Application layer*: Contains application services supporting the business (layer) and the applications that realize them.
- *Technology layer*: Contains technology services supporting the application layer, and hardware and infrastructure that realize them.
- *Physical layer*: Contains elements of the physical world that interplays with IT.
- *Implementation & migration layer*: Contains concepts used to describe how an architecture is going to be realized.
- *Motivation layer*: Contains elements that drive the design and operation of the enterprise.

As for aspects, the full framework identifies *Passive structure*, *Behavior*, *Active structure* and *Motivation* as element types. This is however a simplified version of the element types of the language. To be able to map the user journey concepts to Archimate concepts, we need to examine Archimates element types and Archimates concrete concepts.

4.3. Archimate element types

Archimate created hierarchy models and meta models that specify Archimate's *aspects* into more detail. Derived from the Archimate specification [2], we created the total hierarchy of Archimate's element types, shown in Figure 4. The element types are represented in white boxes and written in italics to show the classes are abstract. Abstract classes cannot be instantiated but serve to structure the language.

Figure 4: Archimate element types: hierarchy [2]

Examining the element types, we see the mentioned aspects of the Archimate framework again: *Active structure element*, *Passive structure element*, *Behavior element* and *Motivation element*. Furthermore, we see that there are three Behavior elements: *External behavior element*, *Internal behavior element* and *event*. For structural elements, we see that Active structure elements can be further subdivided into *Internal* – and *External active structure elements*.

To be able to match user journey concepts to Archimate element types, we need the descriptions of these element types. The descriptions have to be compared to the descriptions of the user journey elements to find proper matches between concepts. For this reason, an overview Archimate element type descriptions, derived from the Archimate specification document, can be found in Table 8, Appendix B.

4.4. Archimate concepts

To map user journey elements to Archimate concepts, we also need an overview of the concrete concepts and their definitions. Derived from Archimate specification document, we created an overview of all concepts (and their notation). The overview is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Archimate concepts [2]

- The *Strategy layer* consists of: {*Resource, Capability and Course of action*}.
- The *Business layer* consists of: {*Business role, Business collaboration, Business interface, Business process, Business function, Business interaction, Business service, Business event, Business object, Contract, Representation and Product*}.
- The *Application layer* consist of: {*Application component, Application collaboration, Application interface, Application process, Application function, Application interaction, Application service, Application event and Data object*}.
- The *Technology layer* consists of: {*Node, Device, System software, Technology collaboration, Technology interface, Technology process, Technology function, Technology interaction, Technology service, Technology event, Artifact, Communication network and Path*}.
- The *Physical layer* consists of: {*Facility, Equipment, Material and Distribution network*}.
- The *Implementation & Migration layer* consists of: {*Work package, Implementation event, Deliverable, Plateau and Gap*}.
- The *Motivation layer* consists of: {*Stakeholder, Driver, Assessment, Value, Meaning, Goal, Outcome, Principle, Requirement and Constraint*}

To be able to match user journey concepts to Archimate concepts in the next section, we will need the descriptions of the Archimate concepts. Hence, derived from the Archimate specification document, an overview of the descriptions of the Archimate concepts is created, shown in Table 9, Appendix B.

As we now explored the Archimate structure and concepts and descriptions, we can now start to map the user journey elements to Archimates elements to create our artefact: User Journey Extension for Archimate (UJEA).

5. User Journey Extension for Archimate (UJEA)

The following section contains the creation of our artefact. In the design procedure of section 4.1 we shortly introduced the 4 components of the artefact: The mapping of concepts, the UJEA meta model, the UJEA graphical notation and the Cross layer meta model. In this section, we discuss all steps that lead to these components. As this is an essential part of the thesis, the tables in this section have a different colour (*orange*). We also mentioned that the procedure of creating UJEA will be explained into more detail in this section. Thus, we start the section with a detailed approach for creating UJEA.

5.1. Low-level approach - UJEA

For creating the artefact, we follow the detailed procedure that is visualized in Figure 6. The steps are coloured in yellow on the left, while the Artefact and its subproducts are shown in a blue container. On the right, the input products from the previous chapters are shown. We start the artefact design by *mapping user journey concepts to Archimate element types* (step 1). In the previous section we gathered and examined Archimates element types, their descriptions and their relations. By comparing the descriptions of user journey concepts with the descriptions of Archimate element types, we can find matching concepts. The matched concepts will be shown in a table, as well as shown in a visual mapping for which we use the Archimate element types hierarchy model as a basis.

Figure 6: Detailed design procedure for User Journey Extended Archimate

Next, we start *mapping user journey concepts to Archimate concepts* (step 2). Just like step 1, we compare the descriptions of user journey concepts with the descriptions of Archimate concepts to find matches. The mapping of concepts will again be shown in a table, as well as a visual mapping. For the visual mapping, we use the visual mapping from the previous step and extend it with the new matches.

What follows is that we create the *User Journey Extension for Archimate (UJEA) meta model* and the *New Archimate Framework* (step 3). Creating the UJEA meta model is actually a small step; we only have to add relationships among user journey concepts in the Extended visual mapping from the previous step. The relationships were already defined in the user journey meta model of subsection 3.2., and can simply be derived and integrated into the Extended visual mapping. For the New Archimate Framework, we simply have to add the user journey domain as a layer or aspect.

After creating the UJEA meta model, we can start creating the *UJEA graphical notation* (step 4). To do this, we first set up some general design guidelines to create a basis for our notation, followed by a graphical notation (shape, icon and colour) for each element.

With the notation finished, we can sketch an example (step 5) with Archi to give an idea of how UJEA can be applied, and how the sizes and positions of the graphical notation should look like. This is however an iterative process; multiple sketches will be drawn until a readable and simplistic version will serve the purpose of the example. We also see that the final requirements from section 4.1 have influence on the whole artefact.

When using Archi to create an example that visualises the user journey elements in the most optimal way, we will see that some relations are not precisely compliant to the UJEA meta model. For this reason, we create an adjusted version of the UJEA meta model (step 6), resulting in a *Platform dependent UJEA meta model*.

As last step, we create the *UJEA cross-layer meta model* to allow links between UJEA's user journey elements and Archimate elements from other layers (step 7). For this step, we follow one of the Archimate cross-layer rules that services of a layer can serve elements of another layer.

5.2. Mapping user journey concepts - Archimate element types

We by matching the descriptions of user journey concepts to the Archimate element types that were introduced in 4.3. This helps us select a subset of potential Archimate concepts to map on each user journey concept. To map user journey concepts to Archimate element types, we will compare the descriptions of user journey concepts of Table 3 (subsection 3.1), with the descriptions of Archimate element types shown in Table 9, Appendix B. The result of this mapping is shown in Table 5 below. For each mapping, a rationale is given that explains the thoughts and decisions behind the mapping.

Table 5: Mapping user journey concepts to Archimate element types

User journey concept	Archimate element type	Rationale
<i>User journey</i>	Passive structure element	When speaking of a user journey, we speak of the journey of a user on a conceptual level. It does not perform behaviour. Instead, user behaviour and experience determine the user journey.
<i>User journey map</i>	Internal behaviour element	The user journey map is the explicit form of the user journey, containing a sequence of activities and experiences that occur by interacting with a company. The map contains user behaviour measured by a company, performed by a <i>persona</i> that represents a user.
<i>Persona</i>	Active structure element	In terms of a user journey map, the activities are performed by a persona. As the persona performs behaviour, it is an active structure element.
<i>Channel</i>	Active structure element	A channel exposes the functionality of a business service to users/customers. As exposing functionality and connecting users with a company can be seen as behaviour, this is an active structure element.
<i>Activity</i>	External behaviour element	As the activities will trigger one another, representing a series of behaviours, an activity is a behaviour element. When further specifying whether activity is internal or external behaviour, we look at who executes the activity: the user. As the user is external seen from the company's perspective, external behaviour element would seem the appropriate match.
<i>Stage</i>	Internal behaviour element	A stage, or phase contains a sequence of activities. The container is however created by the company to provide structure to the series of activities. Hence, stage can be seen as an internal behaviour element.
<i>Experience</i>	Motivation element	Motivation elements drive the design and operation of the enterprise. In other words; motivation elements play part in why an organisation operates as how it does. Organisations aim for a high user/customer experience and take action to improve it. Thus, experience affects the design and operation of the enterprise.
<i>Moment of truth</i>	Motivation element	As the moment of truth is a decision point that influences the rest of the user journey, it also influences the company. Hence, a moment of truth is a motivation element.
<i>Goal</i>	Motivation element	A goal drives the user journey. A goal matches directly with the existing "Goal" element, that is already part of the motivation layer. (<i>Note!</i>) As this is a goal in a journey context, we adjust <i>goal</i> into <i>Journey goal</i> to prevent confusion.
<i>Timeline</i>	Motivation element	Timeline is an indication of time how long a certain stage or user journey map should endure; it represents a condition to be met and thus drives operations and architecture.
<i>Opportunity</i>	Motivation element	An opportunity represents requests for adjustments or new ideas and thus shapes the design and architecture.
<i>Abstraction level</i>	Motivation element	Abstraction level serves as a guideline to shape the user journey (in architecture) on a certain scope/perspective. Therefore, it guides/shapes the design and architecture.
<i>Thought</i>	Motivation element	A thought explains the experience. It shows why a user is negative or why a user is positive. As it answers a "why" question, a thought can be seen as a motivation element.

Having each user journey concept mapped onto an Archimate element type, we can create a visual overview of the mapping. For this, we use the Archimate element types hierarchy from Figure 4 and connect each user journey element to it. The visual mapping of Table 5 is shown in Figure 7. The relation used between the elements is a specialization relation, as each user journey concept is a specialisation of the mapped Archimate element type.

Figure 7: Visual mapping of user journey concepts to Archimate element types

The element types are again shown in white boxes and written in italic to show they are abstract classes that cannot be instantiated (but provide structure to the language). The user journey elements are shown in grey as they are concrete classes (that can be instantiated), except user journey itself, as this was the only abstract concept of our user journey meta model (Figure 2).

5.3. Mapping user journey concepts - Archimate concepts

As our next step of mapping user journeys to Archimate, we map the user journey concepts to the Archimate concepts that were introduced in 4.4.4. To help us with these mappings, Lankhorst (2017) already proposed a set mapping between customer journey concepts and Archimate concepts, shown in Figure 8.

<i>Customer Journey Map</i>	<i>ArchiMate</i>
Persona	Business Role
Customer Journey, Process, Scenario	Business Process
Stage	Business Process
Touchpoint	Business Service
Channel	Business Interface
Experience, Feeling	Metric (specialisation of Driver), or profile attribute
Evaluation	Assessment
Opportunity, Improvement	Requirement

Figure 8: Customer journey mapping to Archimate, proposed by Lankhorst [7]

Although Lankhorst did not add rationals for these mappings, they can still serve as additional support for the mappings we find ourselves. To map the concepts, we compare the descriptions of user journey concepts from Table 3 to the Archimate concept descriptions from Table 9, Appendix B. As we already mapped user journey concepts to Archimate element types, we have already narrowed down the amount of optional mappings to choose from. The mapping of user journey concepts to Archimate concepts is shown in Table 6. Each mapping of concepts is explained with a rationale. The corresponding element types are kept in the table to provide a full overview of all the mapped concepts.

Table 6: Mapping user journey concepts to Archimate element types

User journey concept	Archimate element type	Archimate concept	Rationale
<i>User journey</i>	Passive structure element	Business object	A business object represents a concept within a business domain [2]. The description matches with the description of a user journey; it is still a conceptual element until made explicit with a user journey map.
<i>User journey map</i>	Internal behaviour element	Business process	A business process is a sequence of business behaviours that achieves a specific outcome [2]. A user journey map contains a series of user activities with the corresponding user experience, and thus counts as a series of behaviours. This mapping was also suggested by [7].
<i>Persona</i>	Active structure element	Business role	A business role represents the responsibility for performing specific behaviour to which an actor can be assigned [2]. In other words, a business role is a type of actor. This matches with idea behind a persona: a typical user type that summarizes many different individual users (actors). This mapping was also suggested by [2] and suggested in The Open Group discussion session (Appendix A).
<i>Channel</i>	Active structure element	Interface	A business interface is a point of access where a business service is made available to the environment [2]. As a channel allows the user to access products and services, these concepts seem to be the right match. This mapping was also suggested by [7] and suggested in The Open Group discussion session (Appendix A).
<i>Activity</i>	External behaviour element	Business service	A business service is an explicitly defined exposed business behavior [2] that can be externally executed/used. The Archimate meta model allows business services to trigger one another, creating a series of behaviours. A Business process was also considered as it represents a sequence of behaviours to achieve a certain outcome [2]. Though, a business process is about internal behaviour while the user and his/her actions are external.
<i>Stage</i>	Internal behaviour element	Business process	A stage contains one or multiple activities [2]. In other words, it represents a collection of behaviours. Unlike activity, stage is not executed by the user, but merely serves as container. Thus, a stage can be an internal behaviour element. The mapping was also suggested by Lankhorst [7].
<i>Experience</i>	Motivation element	Metric (Specialisation of Driver)	A metric is the extent, quantity or degree of something [7]. The experience represents a degree: the degree of happiness. The degree of happiness can be presented in strings (happy, unhappy or neutral) or scaled in quantities. This mapping was also suggested by Lankhorst [7] and suggested in The Open Group discussion session (Appendix A).
<i>Moment of truth</i>	Motivation element	Assessment	An assessment is a result of an analysis [2]. The description matches the idea of the moment of truth where the user evaluates the different options in order to make a decision (that determines how the journey will be continued or stopped).
<i>Journey goal*</i>	Motivation element	Goal	A goal is a high-level statement, intent, direction or desired endstate for an organisation or its stakeholders. As the journey goal represents the desired endstate of the persona (that represents multiple users), the journey goal matches the goal concept.
<i>Timeline</i>	Motivation element	Requirement	A requirement is a statement of need that must be met by the architecture [2]. As the timeline is an indicator of how long a stage or journey should take, it serves as a requirement that should be met.
<i>Opportunity</i>	Motivation element	Requirement	An opportunity is a suggested improvement. The suggested improvement can be seen as a need that must be met by the architecture. This mapping was suggested by Lankhorst [7].
<i>Abstraction level</i>	Motivation element	Requirement	The abstraction level is the level of detail of a user journey map. The abstraction level says something about how a user journey map should be created and read. Thus, the abstraction level matches with the description of a requirement.
<i>Thought</i>	Motivation element	Meaning	A meaning is the knowledge, expertise or interpretation of an element in a particular context [2]. A thought is a representation of a user's thinking and interpretations, it matches the description of

* Note that we changed the user journey concept 'Goal' into Journey goal. The name of this concept is changed because Goal is already a concept within Archimate, and this is a goal specific for a (user) journey.

With our mappings finished, we create a visual overview shown in Figure 9. The Archimate element types are again shown in white boxes (written in italics), the Archimate concepts are visualised in light-grey and the user journey concepts in dark-grey (except for the abstract User journey concept that is shown in white).

Figure 9: Visual mapping of user journey concepts to Archimate concepts

5.4. User Journey Extension for Archimate meta model

As we have finished mapping the user journey concepts onto Archimate concepts, we have almost extended Archimate with user journeys. As final step, we need to integrate the relationships among the user journey concepts in Figure 9. These relationships were already established in the user journey meta model from Figure 2, subsection 3.2. However, the composition relationships from the user journey meta model are quite restricting the user's freedom compared to Archimate. Instead, Archimate tends to let the user decide which elements to include. However, Archimate does make certain elements mandatory in the specified viewpoints. In case an architect decides to use such viewpoint, there is of list of concepts that *must* be included. Hence, we replace the *compositions* from the user journey meta model into *aggregations*.

Combining the user journey meta model with the visual mapping of concepts from Figure 9, and replacing the compositions with aggregations, we create our meta model for *User Journey Extension for Archimate* (UJEA), shown in Figure 11). Note that the cardinalities from the user journey meta model have not been implemented in the UJEA meta model. According to Lankhorst, Attributes, instances of entities and cardinalities are not supported in the Archimate meta models as they are "too detailed for the enterprise architecture level of abstraction" [8]. Along with a meta model comes a set of *attributes* for each meta class. However, the attributes remain the same as the identified attributes of the user journey meta model from Table 4 (subsection 3.2.)

As we now have our meta model, we still need to visualise how UJEA can fit in the current Archimate framework that was discussed in subsection 4.4. Comparing the definitions of *layers* (domains) and *aspects* (element types), the user journey extension seems to match more with a domain and thus a new layer must be introduced to the framework. The order of layers is structured from what happens at the front of a company (top of the framework), down to what happens internally (bottom of the framework). As user journeys are experienced by the user, the user journey layer should be placed at the top. Doing so, we extend the Full Archimate Framework as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: New Full Archimate Framework

As we have finished the UJEA meta model and the new Full Archimate Framework, we can start creating a notation, create our first example, and identify potential relationships with other layers to allow a cross-layer model. Hence in our next subsections, we create a notation (5.5.), we create an example (5.6.) and establish the relationships with elements from other layers (5.7.).

Figure 11: User Journey Extended Archimate meta model

5.5 Graphical notation

In this subsection, we will create a notation for User Journey Extension for Archimate. We start with creating a set of guidelines help us shape the notation and ensure the notation will fit the artefacts purpose.

1. Use of orange to denote user journey elements

Following the Archimate layout conventions of Lankhorst [7], colours should be used for emphasis. There is a perceptual order in the colour spectrum that determines the way humans view colours. The colour red seems to draw the most attention; it stands out of all the other colours and tends to focus on the foreground. User journeys happen on the front of a company, which would make red would be a nice match. Though, the implementation and migration layer has already been given the colour red, thus we choose orange, a colour similar to red, as the colour to denote user journey concepts. Another layout convention from Lankhorst [7] says that colours should be used to indicate similarity. To follow the convention, we aim to colour all user journey concepts with an orange tint.

2. Use of shapes of the matched Archimate concepts

Following the Archimate layout conventions of Lankhorst [7], similar shapes should be used for similar concepts. This means that when shapes are similar, people expect that semantics will be similar as well. The convention helps us selecting shapes for the notation of each concept: we already mapped user journey concepts to Archimate concepts that had a matching description. Thus, we can use the shape of the Archimate concept that matches the user journey concept, as users are already familiar to its semantics.

3. Select icons that are generally associated with the corresponding concept

We aim to choose icons that people associate with the concept. This way, the semantics of the elements become self-exploratory through the association people have with that icon.

4. Create a user journey notation that UX designers can understand

During the case study, we observed that architects understand the deliverables of UX designers, but not the other way around. As we chose to extend the language of the enterprise architect, the UX designer might find it difficult to understand the semantics of UJEA. Thus, we tend to create a design similar to the observed UX design journeys at ContextMSP, positioning the elements in a similar way and adding emotions to the journey map (as the observed architect journey examples did not). The guideline sets priority on simplicity and usability and a focus to make it understandable for the UX designer.

As we now have a set of general guidelines, we start creating our notation for UJEA. The notation is shown in Table 7, along with a rationale for each notation. The rationale explains the selected icons, shapes and colours.

Table 7: Notation for UJEA

User journey concept	Notation	Rationale
User journey (abstract)	-	The user journey itself is an <i>abstract concept</i> . Therefore, we do not model the user journey (no notation necessary).
User journey map		For the user journey map, we use the icon that is generally used to depict a journey. Further, we use the shape of a business process. The concepts of a user journey map are visualised inside the user journey map, rather than connecting elements with aggregations and compositions. Following the Archimate layout conventions of Lankhorst [7], crossing lines should be avoided. Additionally, the journey maps exemplified in the problem investigation showed one big rectangle with elements placed inside. Thus, we stick to the design people are already familiar with.
Persona		Although mapped on business role, we take the icon of business actor as the icon associated to a human. Further, we use the shape of a note as notes are made to contain a bunch of text, which will be the case with a persona (showing the persona's properties and goals)
Channel		As shape, we use a rectangle as it represents a passive structural element. As icons, we specify app, website and chatbot as most common digital channels. Thus, we chose icons that are commonly used to represent these systems.
Stage		As stage was mapped on business process, we use both the icon and shape of a business process. The use of an arrow is a common icon for indicating a phase, thus it fits the purpose for indicating a stage.
Experience		Following the Archimate layout conventions of Lankhorst [7], colours should be used to convey emotions. Additionally, requirement 32 and 34 from our requirement list said to use emoticons and colours to represent experience. Observed from the examples in the problem investigation, green is used for positive experience, yellow for neutral experience and red for negative experience.
Moment of truth		Moment of truth was to indicate an important decision was made by the user at a certain moment (activity). Thus, as sign of importance, we use an exclamation mark. The figure was kept small so it can be placed on the activity it belongs to (without taking too much space). The decision itself can already be traced from the thought and activity.
Journey goal		For goal, we stick to the icon and shape of a goal. A bullseye is a common representation for a goal.
Timeline		We choose the shape of a note as it has a plain look; it simply serves the purpose to show the time of a journey map or stage. The time is denoted with a string to give freedom to the user on how to express the time.
Opportunity		For opportunity, we chose an icon of a light bulb. Light bulbs are common for presenting ideas, matching the purpose and meaning of an opportunity. For the shape, we kept the motivation element shape.
Activity		For activity, we use an icon of a hand clicking on something. The 'click' represents a user interaction with the system used as a channel. As shape, we kept the behaviour element shape. We use a light shape as the elements behind it are quite dark. By using this colour contrast, we aim to get the attention of the reader towards the activities.
Abstraction level		Just like for Timeline, we use a simple, plain looking shape to indicate the abstraction level. It gives important information to the reader (The level of detail/scope of the journey) but it is not what we want the journey map reader to focus on.
Thought		A common icon or symbol for thoughts are grey or white clouds. Due to this reason, the clouds are kept grey instead of orange. The shape was already used in Archimate for the concept Meaning, which also happens to be the mapped Archimate concept.

As we finished our notation, we use the notation and defined relations from the UJEA meta model to create an illustrative case that shows how the notation can be applied.

5.6. Illustrative case

In this section, apply the notation to a fictional case to illustrate the use of the notation. For this, we make use of an enterprise architecture tool called Archi. The illustrative case visualises the user journey of transferring money from a savings account to a debit account. The main objective of the illustrative case is to provide a visual example of how the notation can be applied, clarifying the *sizes* and *positions* of notation elements. The illustrative case is shown in Figure 12.

In this case, the user is represented by a *persona* named Bob. The persona is presented on the right, along with the properties and general goals. At the left of the user journey map, we see the *goal*: “Bob wants to have sufficient balance to pay his groceries”. In the middle, we see the *user journey map* with the *abstraction level*: Low. This means that the user journey map is modelled from a detailed perspective. In the middle, we see a large swimlane with a telephone icon that represents the used *Channel*: an app. Within the swimlane, we see three *stages*: Login, Balance check and Transfer money. Each stage has its own *timeline* donated into seconds.

Figure 12: Illustrative case: Transfer money from savings account (user journey)

Within each stage, we see the *activities*, connected by trigger relations. The series of activities shape the scenario that Bob sees that his balance is below zero, and thus he transfers money from his savings account to his debit account. Each activity shows the *experience* of Bob at that time. We see that in general, Bob's emotions are neutral, but at the middle activity he is not very happy he did not receive a message that his debit balance went below zero. In the end, we see that Bob is happy after he quickly transferred the required money. We also see a *moment of truth* connected to the activity where Bob notices his balance is too low, as Bob has to make a decision on what to do, which greatly influences the rest of the user journey. Additionally, we see an *opportunity* mapped onto the moment of truth: Introduce a low balance notification. Having this feature implemented would solve the unhappy status of Bob in this scenario. At last, Bob's *thoughts* are presented on top of the channel, giving extra context and explanation to the activities.

5.7. Platform dependent UJEA meta model

The composition of the notational elements in Figure 12 was created through iterative sketching, varying the positions and sizes of the elements. This sketch turned out to be the most convenient way of presenting the information, but some relationships among elements had to be changed. This means that the example is not compliant to our UJEA meta model. Thus, we adjust the UJEA meta model relationships to be consistent to the relationships visible in the illustrative case. This leads to the creation of the *Platform dependent UJEA meta model*, shown in Figure 13. The adjusted relationships are coloured in orange.

Figure 13: Platform dependent UJEA meta model

As the *Channel* in Figure 12 contained *Stages* and a *Moment of truth* while these elements were optional, there are two new aggregations that go from *Channel* to *Stage* and *Moment of truth*. As *Moment of truth* is not modeled within the *Activity* (as it would reduce readability), we removed the aggregation from *Activity* to *Moment of truth*. Further, the association relation was used between *Opportunity* and *Moment of truth* to show an important user decision can lead to certain *Opportunities*. Hence, the new association link was included. The example also showed that the *User journey map* was linked to a *Journey goal* through an association instead of composition to improve the readability of the *User journey map*. Hence, the composition relationship between these two concepts is changed into an associated with relationship. In the example, *Thoughts* are not contained by the *Activity* anymore, but by the *User journey map*. This explains the aggregation relationship floating from *User journey map* to *Thought*.

5.8. Cross layering: Connecting the user journey to other architecture

To be able to connect a user journey map or specific user journey components to other architecture, we need to specify what elements and through which relationship they can be connected. If we look at the introduced strategy layer and motivation layer in the Archimate specification, it seems a meta model is created that shows which concepts or concept types may be linked to the newly introduced elements (ArchiMate® 3.0.1 Specification, 2019). Hence, we specify the allowed relationships with other Archimate concepts in a meta model, shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: UJEA cross-layer meta model

A *User journey map* as well as an *Activity* can be served by a *Business service*. In Archimate, business services are the common elements to serve a different layer, allowing layers to be connected to one another. That is why Archimate is called a service-oriented modelling language [7]. Further, an *Opportunity* may be connected to a *Business service* or to a *Business function*. As opportunities need to be assigned to development teams, business function is the preferred option. We also see that a *Business interface* can be assigned to a *Channel*, as business interfaces (that correspond to the modelled channel) are commonly modelled within the business layer. We also see that *User journey maps* can be associated by other *User journey maps*. The rest of the relationships are inherited relationships among user journey concepts from the UJEA meta model. In the next chapter we discuss multiple applications of the artefact. Several cross-layer viewpoints will be defined with examples, showing how the UJEA cross-layer meta model can be applied.

6. References

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APPENDIX A: Discussion- The Open Group

Date: 12-3-2019

Location: Capitool 15, Enschede

Attendees: Henk Jonkers, Dick Quartel, Maarten Steen, Lars van den Bos

The following document contains notes of the brainstorm session with three members of The Open Group. During the session, elements of the initial requirement list were discussed. Additionally, The Open Group showed their own customer journey implementation as example [8], which was also examined in the literature study. The discussion lead to requirements being accepted/rejected, but also lead to new requirements for the mapping and the UJEA notation.

**During the interview, the answers of the interviewee were directly written down and summarized, resulting in the documented answers below.*

Initial requirements evaluated

- When discussing the difference between channel and touchpoint, both concepts seem to be perceived as almost similar by The Open Group. The difference is very small: channel seems to be focused on the medium of communication and touchpoint on the interaction itself. From the Archimate perspective, touchpoint would be a behavioural element while channel would be a structural element. Due to this insight, touchpoint and channel cannot be combined: one has to be chosen. To at least show what medium is used, it seems best to choose for implementing channel.
- Channel or Touchpoint, Stage, Experience, Activity, Persona, abstraction level and Goal are necessary elements for UJEA.
- Painpoints should not be implemented in planned journeys as it requires analysis of actual behaviour.
- For visualising the experience, you can use both emoticons and/or colouring, no strong preference.

New requirements

- To map concepts to Archimate, first map the new concepts to element types, then map them to Archimate concepts.
- If touchpoint is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a Business service (behavioural, and external)
- If channel is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a Business interface (structural)
- If activity is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a business service (behavioural, and external)
- If persona is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a role (structural)
- If experience is to be mapped to Archimate, it should be a metric
- If abstraction level is to be implemented, you need predefined abstraction levels. As example, you could have 2 levels, in which level 1 is high level, containing high level activities, whereas level 2 is more detailed, containing low level activities.

APPENDIX B: Archimate descriptions

This appendix contains summaries of Archimate descriptions. The first set contains the descriptions of Archimate element types, represented in Table 8. The second set contains the descriptions of the Archimate concepts. This set is shown in Table 9.

Table 8: Archimate element types and descriptions [2]

Archimate element type descriptions	
Element type	Definition
<i>Behavior element</i>	Element that represents a behavior, denoted by a verb.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Internal behaviour element</i> • <i>External behaviour element</i> • <i>Event</i> 	<p>A unit of activity performed by one or more active structure elements.</p> <p>An explicitly defined exposed behavior, called a service.</p> <p>a behavior element that denotes a state change.</p>
<i>Structure element</i>	Element that can perform behavior, or on which behavior can be performed upon.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Active structure element</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Internal active structure element</i> ○ <i>External active structure element</i> • <i>Passive structure element</i> 	<p>An entity that is capable of performing behavior.</p> <p>An entity that is capable of performing behavior.</p> <p>a point of access where one or more services are provided to the environment, called an interface.</p> <p>A structural element that cannot perform behavior. Active structure elements can perform behavior on passive structure elements.</p>
<i>Motivation element</i>	element that drive the design and operation of the enterprise.

Table 9: Archimate concepts and descriptions [2]

Archimate concept descriptions		
Layer	Concept	Description
Strategy layer	Resource	An asset owned or controlled by an individual or organization.
	Capability	An ability that an active structure element, such as an organization, person, or system, possesses.
	Course of action	An approach or plan for configuring some capabilities and resources of the enterprise, undertaken to achieve a goal.
	Business actor	A business entity that is capable of performing behavior.
	Business role	the responsibility for performing specific behavior, to which an actor can be assigned, or the part an actor plays in a particular action or event.
	Business collaboration	An aggregate of two or more business internal active structure elements that work together to perform collective behavior.
	Business interface	A point of access where a business service is made available to the environment.
	Business process	A sequence of business behaviors that achieves a specific outcome such as a defined set of products or business services.
	Business function	A collection of business behavior based on a chosen set of criteria (typically required business resources and/or competencies), closely aligned to an organization, but not necessarily explicitly governed by the organization.
Business layer	Business interaction	A unit of collective business behavior performed by (a collaboration of) two or more business roles.
	Business service	An explicitly defined exposed business behavior.
	Business event	A business behavior element that denotes an organizational state change. It may originate from and be resolved inside or outside the organization.
	Business object	A concept used within a particular business domain.
	Contract	A formal or informal specification of an agreement between a provider and a consumer that specifies the rights and obligations associated with a product and establishes functional and non-functional parameters for interaction.
	Representation	A perceptible form of the information carried by a business object.
	Product	A coherent collection of services and/or passive structure elements, accompanied by a contract/set of agreements, which is offered as a whole to (internal or external) customers.

Application layer	Application component	An encapsulation of application functionality aligned to implementation structure, which is modular and replaceable. It encapsulates its behavior and data, exposes services, and makes them available through interfaces.
	Application collaboration	An aggregate of two or more application components that work together to perform collective application behavior.
	Application interface	A point of access where application services are made available to a user, another application component, or a node.
	Application process	A sequence of application behaviors that achieves a specific outcome.
	Application function	Automated behavior that can be performed by an application component.
	Application interaction	A unit of collective application behavior performed by (a collaboration of) two or more application components.
	Application service	An explicitly defined exposed application behavior.
	Application event	An application behavior element that denotes a state change.
	Data object	Data structured for automated processing.
Technology layer	Node	A computational or physical resource that hosts, manipulates, or interacts with other computational or physical resources.
	Device	A physical IT resource upon which system software and artifacts may be stored or deployed for execution
	System software	Software that provides or contributes to an environment for storing, executing, and using software or data deployed within it.
	Technology collaboration	An aggregate of two or more nodes that work together to perform collective technology behavior.
	Technology interface	A point of access where technology services offered by a node can be accessed.
	Technology process	A sequence of technology behaviors that achieves a specific outcome.
	Technology function	A collection of technology behavior that can be performed by a node.
	Technology interaction	A unit of collective technology behavior performed by (a collaboration of) two or more nodes.
	Technology service	An explicitly defined exposed technology behavior.
	Technology event	A technology behavior element that denotes a state change.
	Artifact	A piece of data that is used or produced in a software development process, or by deployment and operation of an IT system.
Communication network	A set of structures that connects computer systems or other electronic devices for transmission, routing, and reception of data or data-based communications such as voice and video.	
	Path	A link between two or more nodes, through which these nodes can exchange data or material.
Physical layer	Facility	A physical structure or environment.
	Equipment	One or more physical machines, tools, or instruments that can create, use, store, move, or transform materials.
	Material	Tangible physical matter or physical elements.
	Distribution network	A physical network used to transport materials or energy.
Implementation & Migration layer	Work package	A series of actions identified and designed to achieve specific results within specified time and resource constraints.
	Implementation event	A behavior element that denotes a state change related to implementation or migration.
	Deliverable	A precisely-defined outcome of a work package.
	Plateau	A relatively stable state of the architecture that exists during a limited period of time.
	Gap	A statement of difference between two plateaus.
Motivation layer	Stakeholder	Role of an individual, team, or organization (or classes thereof) that represents their interests in the outcome of the architecture.
	Driver	An external or internal condition that motivates an organization to define its goals and implement the changes necessary to achieve them.
	Assessment	The result of an analysis of the state of affairs of the enterprise with respect to some driver.
	Value	Relative worth, utility, or importance of a core element or an outcome.
	Meaning	Knowledge or expertise present in, or the interpretation given to, a core element in a particular context.
	Goal	A high-level statement of intent, direction, or desired end state for an organization and its stakeholders.
	Outcome	An end result that has been achieved.
	Principle	A qualitative statement of intent that should be met by the architecture.
	Requirement	A statement of need that must be met by the architecture.
	Constraint	A factor that prevents or obstructs the realization of goals.